

Unknown Knowns: The non-enforcement of gambling legislation in Ireland and the function of opaque and divided information systems

Frank Houghton¹

The history of state-sanctioned gambling and state involvement in gambling in Ireland can probably be best described as murky at best. This can be seen across a range of domains from the significant level of corruption which was finally exposed in the pseudo-charitable Irish Hospital Sweepstakes (Coleman, 2009; Corless, 2010), to the implausible arguments about winning bets put forward by a former Taoiseach (Prime Minister) to an investigating Tribunal to account for illicit payments (see figure one).

Figure One: Statement by former Taoiseach Bertie Ahern to the Mahon Tribunal

Source: Irish Examiner; Mahon Tribunal of Inquiry,

The Irish gambling industry was recently estimated to be worth approximately €10 billion per year (Michael, 2019), with numerous reports indicating ongoing general growth, particularly in the online arena (Business World, 2021; McGarry, 2021; McGarry, 2021). Growth in Ireland is not isolated, with the global gambling industry

forecast to rise from a turnover of US\$ 711.4 Billion in 2020 to US\$ 876 Billion by 2026 (Cision PR Newswire, 2022).

Significant concerns over the negative impacts of gambling in Ireland have been raised in many quarters (College of Psychiatrists of Ireland, 2020; NACDA, 2018; Mongan et al., 2022), including by the country's President (Price, 2018; Holland, 2021; Burnhill, 2023). Concerns have also been raised over the tactics being used by the Gambling industry in Ireland to sway both the public and politicians (Murray, 2022; Houghton, 2022a; Houghton, 2022b). However, despite the well-publicised dangers of gambling, the Irish Government has recently passed the Gambling Regulation Act, 2024, which has established a clear framework for the operation of gambling in Ireland. This Act will undoubtedly provide clarity and stability that will facilitate further expansion by gambling operators. A major component of this legislation is the establishment of the Gambling Regulatory Authority of Ireland (GRAI). Although controls on gambling are included in this Act, for example, in relation to advertising, they are only significant if enforced. The Gambling Regulation Act 2024 will also serve to further normalise gambling in Ireland. Previously, many aspects of gambling in Ireland required approval by a Garda (police) Superintendent in a given district, or approval by a District Court. The Gambling Registration Act instead transfers these functions to the GRAI to oversee, which will inevitably help to normalise such gambling. There is also likely to be an increase in some forms of local gambling as small-scale lotteries, subject to a prize limit of €5,000, no longer require a licence. This represents a doubling of the pre-Act maximum sum of €2,500. This will serve to increase what may be termed aleagenic environments, i.e. environments that promote gambling behaviours.

The rhetoric being used to frame the new Act has focused strongly on the modernisation and reform of existing legislation. A typical appraisal of the legislation in the media includes statements such as: *'It is a major reform of gambling laws, the first in half a century, updating the Gaming and Lotteries Act 1956 and the even older Betting Act 1931'* (McGee, 2022).

Would-be concerns about the liberalisation in the Act are presumably supposed to be assuaged by an intense focus in the media on the potential penalties for operators who break the new law (see Figure Two).

Figure Two: Example Media Coverage of the Penalties Associated with the Gambling Reform Bill

‘What penalties will the companies face?’

There will be substantial administrative penalties (up to €20 million or 10 per cent of takeover) for companies that breach the law. In extremis, there will be prison sentences of up to eight years for serious breaches, including failure to protect children from gambling.’

Source: McGee, 2022

This form of State posturing is not unusual in Ireland, but minimal enforcement is the norm. This is evident in such fields as tobacco and alcohol control, road traffic enforcement, as well as in the environmental sphere (Department of Justice, 2016; Independent, 2017; Disclosures Tribunal, 2017a; 2017b; 2022; Lynch et al., 2019; Houghton et al., 2020; Purves et al., 2022; Houghton & Lombard, 2024). As a former Tánaiste Mary Harney, Minister for Enterprise and Employment, once commented, *‘Geographically we are closer to Berlin than Boston. Spiritually, we are probably a lot closer to Boston than Berlin’* (Fischer, 2014). Light-touch regulation is very much the norm in Ireland. Many of the laws in Ireland that cover such basics as equality legislation and even workplace health and safety are the result of being a member of the European Community/European Union rather than having been internally driven.

Given the large-scale absence of enforcement of legislation in Ireland and the largely uncritical media coverage that accompanied the Government’s charm offensive to promote the Gambling Regulation Act, it was opportune to explore gambling convictions in more detail. Much of the Government and media coverage specifically mentioned child protection in the proposed legislation (see Figure Two). Therefore, the decision was made to explore in more depth the history

of prosecutions related to underage gambling, including the National Lottery, in Ireland.

It was immediately interesting to note that when this was initially discussed with colleagues with a legal background who taught law in higher education, there was a lack of clarity as to where to proceed in order to access this information. An examination of the Annual Reports of An Garda Síochána (the Irish police force) did not throw light on this matter (e.g. An Garda Síochána, 2021). However, this was not surprising as, in recent years, Garda statistics have come under increasing criticism (Houghton, 2018). Similar to the UK (Travis, 2014), the Government's Central Statistics Office (CSO) now classifies statistics from An Garda Síochána as 'under reservation' due to issues around quality (CSO, 2023). Despite guidance on crime recording (An Garda Síochána, 2020), investigations have identified significant deficits in Garda recording of crimes and incidents, with notable problems also evident in the main IT system, PULSE, used by An Garda Síochána (Garda Síochána Inspectorate, 2014).

Therefore, as outlined in Figure Three, a multi-pronged approach was adopted to try and access data on convictions related to youth gambling in Ireland. Initial attempts to access this data through the Minister of State at the Department of Justice and Equality with responsibility for Law Reform, and the Central Statistics Office were unsuccessful, In both cases it was suggested that contact be made with the Courts Service. The Courts Service found no evidence of any such convictions but noted that their information *'system tracks cases using offence codes, used by prosecutors, who can use free text codes. Unfortunately reports can not be run on free text codes'*.

Figure Three: Interaction with State Agencies in (vain) Attempts to Access Information on Underage Gambling Convictions.

At the same time a request was also made to the Office of the Director of Public Prosecutions. Their response indicated that such convictions were dealt with by An Garda Síochána, and that a Freedom of Information (FOI) Act request should be used to access this information. Initially an FOI request seemed excessive and a simple request for information was sent. This request was acknowledged, but despite several follow-ups, no information was forthcoming. After three months of waiting a formal Freedom of Information (FOI) Act request was made. However, as can be seen from the email response from An Garda Síochána below this was refused on the basis that:

Part 1(n) of Schedule 1 of the FOI Act states that An Garda Síochána is listed as a partially included agency “insofar as it relates to administrative records relating to human resources, or finance or procurement matters”. Therefore, only administrative records that relate to human resources, finance or procurement shall be considered.

Schumacher, the well-known author of the classic text *Small is Beautiful*, stated in another of his works that ‘You must realize your nonknowledge, what you don’t know. The inner attitude if you think

you know is quite different from the attitude when you know you don't know. You're much more observant, more alert' (Schumacher, 1980: 83). This growth-oriented approach is to be admired. However, in contrast, the reality in Ireland is neatly summed-up by Fintan O'Toole from The Irish Times who expands on the Johari Window schema previously articulated by Donald Rumsfeld, former United States Secretary of Defense:

The eloquence of Irish life is often an immensely skilful slalom of evasive manoeuvres. The obstacles we evade are not really secrets. They're what I've called elsewhere unknown knowns – things we know damn well but somehow manage not to know at all...the things we don't want to talk about are made somehow non-existent. We unknow them....The whole point is that it must be allowed to happen but must not be acknowledged as a reality. It must be continually, systemically unknown. It must inhabit silence. (O'Toole, 2015)

The difficulty in accessing information related to youth gambling in Ireland is not accidental. Chomsky (2012) has written about 'intentional ignorance and its uses'. The systems are designed not to be efficient or transparent. This opacity and confusion are deliberate. It performs a clear function. Its function is to allow the Government to grandstand and posture, making idle threats about jail terms and fines of up to €20 million if gambling operators break the law. The reality is that in all likelihood, there will be no jail terms, and fines, if any, will be minimal. For example, despite ongoing issues around youth participation in the National Lottery and scratch card sales to children in Ireland, no fines or prosecutions have been forthcoming on this issue (Regulator of the National Lottery, 2019). Since the Irish National Lottery was established in the mid-1980s only one fine was ever levied by the Office of the Regulator of the National Lottery. This was in 2022, and was for just €150,000 (Regulator of the National Lottery, 2023). Such a fine is a paltry sum considering lotto sales in that year were €884.1 million.

The extensive smokescreen of threats and assurances by the Government is designed to camouflage the establishment of

regulatory certainty for gambling operations in Ireland in the form of the Gambling Regulation Act, 2024. The opaque information systems operated by the State in fields related to the courts and police (An Garda Síochána) neatly help to prevent a clear challenge to assurances around protections contained in the Bill. They function, therefore, exactly as required.

Notes

1. Frank Houghton, Social Sciences ConneXions, Technological University of the Shannon, Limerick, Ireland. Frank.Houghton@TUS.ie

References

An Garda Síochána (2020) Guide to How Crime is Recorded and Counted by An Garda Síochána. Dublin: An Garda Síochána. See: <https://www.cso.ie/en/media/csoie/releasespublications/documents/ep/recordedcrimedetection/2020/guide-to-how-crime-is-counted-and-recorded.pdf>

An Garda Síochána (2021) Annual Report. Dublin: An Garda Síochána.

Burnhill, E. (2023, May 19) President says gambling wrecking much of sport. RTÉ. See: <https://www.rte.ie/news/2023/0519/1384548-coolmine-higgins/>

Business World (2021, August 31) Gambling Continues To Increase In Popularity In Ireland. Business World. See: <https://www.businessworld.ie/news/Gambling-Continues-to-Increase-in-Popularity-in-Ireland-575279.html>

Central Statistics Office (2023) Recorded Crime Detection. CSO. See: <https://www.cso.ie/en/methods/surveybackgroundnotes/recordedcrimedetection/>

Chomsky, N. (2012). New Generation Draws the Line. New York: Routledge.

Cision PR Newswire (2022) Global Gambling Market to Reach \$876 Billion by 2026. See: <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/global-gambling-market-to-reach-876-billion-by-2026-301305923.html>

Coleman, M. (2009) The Irish Sweep: A History of the Irish Hospitals Sweepstake, 1930-87, Dublin: University College Dublin Press.

College of Psychiatrists of Ireland (2020) Gambling Disorder Position Paper. EAP/01/20 approved by Council April 2020. Dublin: College of Psychiatrists of Ireland.

Corless, D. (2010) *The Greatest Bleeding Hearts Racket in the World: Irish Hospitals Sweepstakes*. Dublin: Gill & Macmillan.

Department of Justice (2016) *Commission of Investigation (Certain Matters Relative to the Cavan / Monaghan Division of the Garda Síochána)*. Final Report. Dublin: Department of Justice.

Disclosures Tribunal (2017a) *First interim report of the tribunal of inquiry into protected disclosures made under the Protected Disclosures Act 2014 and certain other matters*. Dublin: Disclosures Tribunal. <https://www.disclosuretribunal.ie/first-interim-report-of-the-tribunal-of-inquiry-into-protected-disclosures-made-under-the-protected-disclosures-act-2014-and-certain-other-matters-was-laid-before-both-houses-of-the-oireachtas-on-the/>

Disclosures Tribunal (2017b) *Second interim report of the tribunal of inquiry into protected disclosures made under the Protected Disclosures Act 2014 and certain other matters*. Dublin: Disclosures Tribunal.

Disclosures Tribunal (2022) *Third interim report of the tribunal of inquiry into protected disclosures made under the Protected Disclosures Act 2014 and certain other matters*. Dublin: Disclosures Tribunal. <https://www.disclosuretribunal.ie/the-third-interim-report-of-the-tribunal-of-inquiry-into-protected-disclosures-made-under-the-protected-disclosures-act-2014-and-certain-other-matters-reporting-on-matters-dealing-with-the-conduct-of/>

Fischer J. (2014) *Boston or Berlin? Reflections on a Topical Controversy, the Celtic Tiger and the World of Irish Studies*. *The Irish Review*, 48: 81-95.

Garda Síochána Inspectorate (2014) *Crime Investigation*. Dublin: Garda Síochána Inspectorate. See <https://www.gsinsp.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Crime-Investigation-Full-Report.pdf>

Holland, K. (2021, June 29) *Gambling ads causing ‘so much damage to families’ – Michael D Higgins*. *The Irish Times*. See: <https://www.irishtimes.com/news/social-affairs/gambling-ads-causing-so-much-damage-to-families-michael-d-higgins-1.4607086>

Houghton, F. (2018) *Something is rotten in the state of Ireland: the Irish Police (An Garda Síochána) and their official statistics*. *The Journal of Radical Statistics*, 120: 38-45.

Houghton, F. (2022a) *Researching Gambling: Have we learned nothing from Big Tobacco’s overt manipulation of science?* *South Eastern European Journal of Public Health*. Special Volume 6. DOI:10.11576/seejph-5769

Houghton, F. (2022b) Feigning Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Through Health Washing: Gambling Industry Conflicts of Interest in Health Service Provision and Training in Ireland. *Medicina Internacia Revuo - International Medicine Review*. 30(118).

Houghton, F. & Lombard, J. (2024) An Examination of the Enforcement of Ireland's Public Health (Alcohol) Act 2018: A Paper Tiger. *ADDICTA: Turkish Journal on Addictions*, 11(3):324-330.

Houghton, F., O'Doherty, D. & Houghton, B. (2020) Teeth or no teeth: Exploring Punitive Measures for Adults Smoking in Cars Containing Children in Aotearoa/ New Zealand. *New Zealand Medical Journal*, 33(1508): 118-122.

Independent. (2017, December 1). Hundreds of gardai abused driving penalty point system as fines and points wiped. *The Independent*. See: <https://m.independent.ie/breaking-news/irish-news/hundreds-of-gardai-abused-driving-penalty-point-system-as-fines-and-points-wiped-36370346.html>

Irish Examiner (2005, June 5) £8,000 won on horses put into daughters' accounts. *Irish Examiner*. <https://www.irishexaminer.com/news/arid-20064326.html>

Lynch, M.J., Stretesky, P.B., & Long, M.A. (2019) Environmental crime prosecutions in Ireland, 2004–2014. *International Journal of Comparative and Applied Criminal Justice*, 43(4): 277-293. DOI: 10.1080/01924036.2019.1615520

Mahon Tribunal of Inquiry (2012) The Tribunal of Inquiry into Certain Planning Matters and Payments. See: <https://www.planningtribunal.ie/reports/>

McGarry, P. (2021, January 18) 'Frightening' rise in online gambling during Covid-19, reports Limerick treatment centre. *Irish Examiner*. See: : <https://www.irishexaminer.com/news/arid-40209329.html>

McGarry, P. (2021 March 25) Numbers seeking help for gambling problems rises during pandemic. *The Irish Times*. See: <https://www.irishtimes.com/news/social-affairs/numbers-seeking-help-for-gambling-problems-rises-during-pandemic-1.4520358>

McGee, H. (2022, November 17) Gambling laws: How will new rules for bookies, casinos and online work? *The Irish Times*. See: <https://www.irishtimes.com/politics/2022/11/17/irelands-new-gambling-law-how-will-it-work/>

Michael, N. (2019, December 23) €10bn staked by Irish gamblers in 2019 dubbed a 'very worrying' statistic. Irish Examiner. See: <https://www.irishexaminer.com/news/arid-30972076.html>

Murray, S. (2022, May 26) Politicians attending bookmaker-hosted event 'doesn't help' ahead of gambling law reform. Irish Examiner. See: <https://www.irishexaminer.com/news/arid-40881836.html>

Mongan, D., Millar, S.R., Doyle, A., Chakraborty, S. & Galvin, B. (2022) Gambling in the Republic of Ireland: Results from the 2019–20 National Drug and Alcohol Survey. Dublin: Health Research Board.

National Advisory Committee on Drugs and Alcohol (NACDA) (2016) Prevalence of Drug Use and Gambling in Ireland and Drug use in Northern Ireland 2014/15. Dublin: National Advisory Committee on Drugs and Alcohol.

O'Toole, F. (2015, September 15) Fintan O'Toole: Shining light on abortion – one of Ireland's 'unknown knowns'. The Irish Times. See: <https://www.irishtimes.com/opinion/fintan-o-toole-shining-light-on-abortion-one-of-ireland-s-unknown-knowns-1.2351430>

Price, R. (2018, July 30) President Michael D. Higgins calls for ban on gambling advertising in sport. The Irish Post. See: <https://www.irishpost.com/news/president-michael-d-higgins-calls-ban-gambling-advertising-sport-157877>

Purves, R.I., Gadsby, E.W., Howell, R., et al. (2022) Alcohol Marketing Restrictions: Learning from International Implementation. A report prepared for Alcohol Focus Scotland. Stirling: Institute for Social Marketing and Health, Faculty of Health Sciences and Sport, University of Stirling.

Regulator of the National Lottery (2019) Annual Report 2018. Dublin: Office of the Regulator of the National Lottery.

Regulator of the National Lottery (2023) Annual Report 2022. Dublin: Office of the Regulator of the National Lottery.

Schumacher, E.F. (1980) Good Work. London: Abacus.

Travis, A. (2014, January 15) Police crime figures lose official status over claims of fiddling. The Guardian. See: <https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2014/jan/15/police-crime-figures-status-claims-fiddling>